

C₁₆TAB catalyzed oxidative decolorisation of methylene blue by acidic *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide

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Abstract : Kinetics and mechanism of uncatalyzed and C₁₆TAB catalyzed oxidation of methylene blue (phenothiazin-5-inum, 3,7-(dimethyl amino)-chloride) [MB⁺] by *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide in acidic media has been studied spectrophotometrically. With excess concentrations of other reactants, the reaction rate follows pseudo-first order kinetics with respect to methylene blue. The uncatalyzed reaction has fractional order dependence on chloramine-T and zero order dependence on H⁺ concentration (in the range $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ to $9.0 \times 10^{-2} M$). Cationic surfactant cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide catalyzes the reaction even before its CMC. A bathochromic shift is the evidence of dye-surfactant interaction. The pre-micellar kinetics has been rationalized in the light of Piskiewicz positive co-operativity. Positive co-operativity index ($n = 1.27$) has been computed. Variations of ionic strength have no influence on the reaction rate. The basic stoichiometry equation is as follows :

where, $\text{P}_2^+ = 4aH$ -phenothiazine-3,7-diamine 5-oxide. On the basis of product analysis a pertinent mechanism is proposed.

Keywords : Chloramine-T, methylene blue, C₁₆TAB, Piskiewicz, pre-micellar.

Introduction

Methylene blue, an intense blue dye soluble in water, is a phenothiazine class dye which exhibits a sharp absorption peak in the visible region ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 665 \text{ nm}$) and there is no shift due to variation in acidic pH. Methylene blue is a heterocyclic aromatic compound. Methylene blue is widely used a redox as indicator in analytical chemistry. It is known as a staining and sensitizing agent in biological reactions¹. Due to its stability, it has long residence time in water and is hazardous in aquatic system^{2,3}. Thus, to treat this coloured wastewater containing dyes is a necessary aspect for human welfare and sustainable environment. Increasing concern about colour in the effluent is leading to the worldwide efforts to develop a more efficient colour removing process. Therefore, oxidation of methylene blue (MB⁺) by *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide has been carried out in order to optimize the reaction conditions to develop a more efficient colour removing chemical oxidation method. *N*-Chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide (*p*-Me-C₆H₄SO₂NCINa.1.5H₂O) ab-

breiated, as CAT is the widely studied oxidant^{4,5}. The oxidative depletion of dye was found to be catalyzed by the cationic detergent, C₁₆TAB. Detergents are tending to form micelles. Micelle acts as a kind of micro-reactor. The micelles may increase the reactant concentration within the hydrophilic or hydrophobic areas and cause a favourable orientation of the reactants by polarity gradients. Therefore, C₁₆TAB catalyzed oxidative depletion of MB⁺ by *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide has been investigated. The addition of C₁₆TAB to the dye solution brings about hypsochromic shifts. This spectral shift due to the dye-surfactant interaction leads to the possibility of evolution an analytical method for the determination of C₁₆TAB surfactant that is discussed elsewhere⁶.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of analaR grade and the double distilled water was used throughout to prepare the solutions. An aqueous solution of *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide (Merck) was prepared and standardized periodically by the iodometric method and preserved in an am-

ber-coloured bottle until further use. The aqueous solution of MB^+ (Aldrich) was prepared by dissolving 0.0374 g of MB^+ in 100 cm^3 of water. Working solution was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. The stock solution of C_{16}TAB (Aldrich) was prepared by dissolving 0.0364 g of C_{16}TAB in 100 cm^3 of water. Stock solution of H_2SO_4 was prepared by diluting the calculated volume (from density) of acid with distilled water and finally its concentration was determined by titrating it against standard NaOH solution using phenolphthalein as indicator.

Kinetic procedure :

In all experiments the pseudo-first order kinetics with respect to methylene blue was monitored at 660 nm, using Systronics UV-Vis spectrophotometer. No interference from other reagents, intermediates or product was observed at 660 nm. Beer's law was valid for the measurement under the experimental conditions considered. The total initial volume of the reaction mixture was always kept 10 ml and at $(25.0 \pm 0.1)^\circ\text{C}$. Reagent solutions were mixed in the orders of requisite volumes of methylene blue, sulphuric acid, plus catalyst and water or other reagents where necessary. Separately thermally equilibrated solution of *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide was added to commence the reaction. After vigorous mixing, solution was transferred to spectrophotometer cell. In all the experiments, the reactions were followed up to two half lives. A constant ionic strength of the reaction mixture was maintained by adding required amount of sodium sulphate solution.

Stoichiometry : It was determined using varying ratio of oxidant to methylene blue were thermostated at 25°C for 24 h incubation. The absorbance at 660 nm was measured and residual CAT was determined iodometrically using standard sodium thiosulfate as titrant and potassium iodide-starch as an indicator. The mole ratio (no. of moles of oxidant consumed per mol of MB) was calculated.

The representative stoichiometry of reaction can be depicted as

where, $\text{P}_2^+ = 4aH$ -phenothiazine-3,7-diamine 5-oxide.

Product analysis : The product analysis was done by

mixing 1 *M* sulphuric acid (100 ml), MB^+ (300 mg) and *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide (5 g). The mixture was allowed to stand for 24 h. The organic components were partitioned with diethyl ether. Using benzene-ethyl acetate mixture (8 : 2) as an eluent, preliminary studies were carried out by thin-layer chromatography. The IR spectrum of major separated sample showed strong absorption peak at about $3261\text{--}3360 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ showing the presence of aromatic amino group. The absorption band at 1598, 1562 and 1528 cm^{-1} may be due to the $\text{C}=\text{C}$ stretching. The absorption peaks at 1389 and 1305 cm^{-1} indicate the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ vibrations. The absence of strong absorption bands at $1305\text{--}1160 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ excludes the possibility of sulphone. The absorption peaks at 1097 cm^{-1} most likely due to $\text{S}=\text{O}$ stretching vibrations. An intense peak between $1300\text{--}1200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is expected for $\text{N}\text{--}\text{O}$ stretching, is absent. Therefore, oxidation at nitrogen atom and formation of *N*-oxide in the heterocyclic ring is unlikely, where, $\text{P}_2^+ = 4aH$ -phenothiazine-3,7-diamine 5-oxide.

Results and discussion

Reaction under chosen conditions follows pseudo-first order kinetics with respect to MB^+ . The mean pseudo-first order rate constant k_o' was found $1.7 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. For the determination of dependency of oxidation reaction on [*N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide], the concentration of CAT was varied over a wide range, while that of other reactants were kept constants. The Table 1 summa-

Table 1. Order with respect to *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide
 $[\text{MB}^+] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$,
 Temp. = $(25 \pm 0.1)^\circ\text{C}$

[<i>N</i> -Chloro- <i>p</i> -toluenesulfonamide] $\times 10^4$ (<i>M</i>)	$k' \times 10^2$ (s^{-1})
5.0	0.66
6.0	0.81
7.0	0.90
8.0	1.20
9.0	1.60
10.0	1.70

Mean of duplicate experiments.

rized the results obtained at constant ionic strength. Plot of $\log k_o'$ vs \log [*N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide] gave a straight-line with slope 1.56 (Fig. 1) suggesting the reaction has fractional order dependency with respect to [*N*-

Fig. 1. Order with respect to oxidant : [MB⁺] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, temp. 25 °C.

chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide]. Double reciprocal plot of k^{-1} vs $[N\text{-chloro-}p\text{-toluenesulfonamide}]^{-1}$ at constant substrate and acid concentration has been found to be linear with definite intercept. This kinetic evidence of complex formation between substrate and oxidant further supports the validity of the proposed mechanism. The experimental results revealed that increase in the concentrations of sulfuric acid (1.0 × 10⁻² to 6.0 × 10⁻² M) does not affect the reaction rate i.e. reaction has zero order dependence with respect to H⁺ concentration. With the employed reactant concentration [MB⁺] = 1.5 × 10⁻⁵ M, [H⁺] = 1.0 × 10⁻² M, [N-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M, the initial ionic strength of reaction mixture was 0.036. The variation of ionic strength was done from 0.03 to 0.105 by the addition of sodium sulphate (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of variation in ionic strength

[MB⁺] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁵ M, [N-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide] = 1.0 × 10⁻² M, [H⁺] = 1.0 × 10⁻² M, Temp. = (25 ± 0.1) °C

Ionic strength	$k' \times 10^2$ (s ⁻¹)
0.030	1.7
0.045	2.0
0.060	2.0
0.075	2.5
0.090	1.7
0.105	1.8

Mean of duplicate experiments.

In order to understand the role of cationic surfactant i.e. cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide, the reaction has been studied at different concentrations of C₁₆TAB while

keeping the other factors constant. The results are summarized in Table 3. In the present case C₁₆TAB catalyzes the reaction in the pre-micellar region (1.0 × 10⁻⁶ to 6.0 × 10⁻⁶ M). The plot of log k_o' vs [C₁₆TAB] gives a straight line (Fig. 2). The reported CMC of C₁₆TAB is

Table 3. Variation in C₁₆TAB concentration

[MB⁺] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁵ M, [N-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide] = 1.0 × 10⁻² M, [H⁺] = 1.0 × 10⁻² M, Temp. = (25 ± 0.1) °C

[C ₁₆ TAB] × 10 ⁶ (M)	$k' \times 10^2$ (s ⁻¹)
-	1.7
1.0	2.4
2.0	3.4
3.0	4.3
4.0	4.8
5.0	5.5
6.0	14.0

Mean of duplicate experiments.

Fig. 2. C₁₆TAB catalysis : [MB⁺] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³, [N-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide] = 1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, temp. 25 °C.

9.2 × 10⁻⁴ M at 25 °C. Addition of C₁₆TAB to the solution of methylene blue does not produce turbidity and a clear solution was obtained. The spectral studies revealed a bathochromic shift from 660 to 675 nm in the presence of C₁₆TAB. This provides an evidence for the interaction of C₁₆TAB with the methylene blue. Since the dye molecule and surfactant both are cationic in nature, thus obviously the cause of interaction is hydrophobic that overweighs the electronic repulsion. This interaction results in penetration of dye molecules in to the micelles.

This interactive localization of the reacting species in the relatively small volume of the pseudo-micellar phase compared to the bulk solution leads to a large increase in the effective concentration and the observed rate increases accordingly. Reports are available for pre-micellar catalysis⁷⁻⁹ suggesting that substrate promotes micellization of cationic surfactants or that the small aggregates of the detergent exist below the CMC and they catalyze the reaction. The catalysis by C₁₆TAB has therefore been treated by a theme proposed by Piskiewicz¹⁰. This scheme includes the decomposition of substrate micelle complex in to the free components; resulting in an equation of the following form :

$$\log [(k_{\text{obs}} - k_0)/(k_m - k_{\text{obs}})] = n \log [D] - \log k_D$$

From the above equation the plot of $\log [(k_{\text{obs}} - k_0)/(k_m - k_{\text{obs}})]$ vs $\log [D]$ is linear (Fig. 3) with a slope $n = 1.27$ called the index of co-operativity.

Fig. 3. Piskiewicz model : $[MB^+] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[N\text{-chloro-}p\text{-toluenesulfonamide}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. 25 °C.

The effect of PTS on the rate of oxidation was studied by taking various concentrations of PTS keeping the concentrations of other reactants constant at constant temperature. Oxidation rate decreased with the increase in the concentration of PTS. The decrease in reaction rate supports our assumption that HOCl is main oxidizing species in accordance with the following equilibrium¹¹.

Mechanism :

Chloramine-T behaves as a strong electrolyte and in

acidic media it furnishes various oxidising species.

(*N*-Chlorotoluene-*p*-sulfonamide)

(Dichloramine-T)

(Hypochlorous acid)

(Protonated species)

In our experimental studies the rate of reaction is retarded by addition of PTS, which suggests that the eq. (5) must be preceded by rate determining step. The neutral salt effect supports the participation of neutral molecule in rate determining step. HOCl acid may be considered as the main oxidizing species for the reaction which proceeds slowly in sulfuric acid. The linear double reciprocal plot of k^{-1} vs $[N\text{-chloro-}p\text{-toluenesulfonamide}]^{-1}$ with intercept on Y-axis suggests the formation of a complex between substrate and oxidant⁶. On this basis, following mechanism has been envisaged (Scheme 1).

Surfactant catalyzed mechanism :

Addition of aqueous solution of C₁₆TAB to the solution of methylene blue shows hyperchromic shift. The cause of interaction is electrostatic interaction that overweighs the electronic repulsion. This interactive localization of the reacting species in the relatively small volume of the micelles compared to the bulk solution leads to a large increase in the effective concentration and as a result in the observed rate (in terms of moles per unit time per litre of the entire solution). In the present case as described earlier in the Piskiewicz model¹⁰, Menger and Portney's model¹² we have seen that there is a substrate promoted micellization and a pseudo phase has also come into exist. Since Raghavan and Srinivasan's model¹³ has not been found applicable suggesting that both the reactants are not distributed in the pseudo phase, we propose the following reaction mechanism (Scheme 2) in the presence of C₁₆TAB.

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where, P_2^+ = 4aH-phenothiazine-3,7-diamine 5-oxide

Scheme 1

The chemistry of remaining reaction scheme is same as for the uncatalyzed reaction. The Scheme 2 is pro-

posed for catalysis by C₁₆TAB. As per the reaction mechanism proposed by Bruice *et al.*¹⁴ assumption begins with

Scheme 2

the interaction of substrate MB^+ and a number of D molecules aggregate to form catalytic micelles.

Bathochromic shift is the spectroscopic evidence of association of the dye with the detergent. The chemistry of remaining reaction scheme is same as for the uncatalyzed reaction.

Rate law :

Bathochromic shift in presence of the oxidant is the spectroscopic evidence of interaction between the dye molecule, $C_{16}TAB$, and the oxidizing species. The rate equation for the uncatalyzed reaction between MB^+ and *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide can be represented as follows :

$$r = -d[MB^+]/dt$$

$$= k_o [MB^+] [N\text{-chloro-}p\text{-toluenesulfonamide}]^{3/2} \quad (7)$$

when [*N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide] is in excess, the above equation reduces to

$$r = k'_o [MB^+] \quad (8)$$

where the pseudo-first order rate constant for uncatalyzed reaction is $k'_o = k_o [N\text{-chloro-}p\text{-toluenesulfonamide}]^{3/2}$.

In the presence of the $C_{16}TAB$, the oxidation reaction proceeds through both uncatalyzed and catalyzed pathways. Therefore, the following represents the rate of depletion of MB^+ in the presence of catalyst under excess [*N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide] and acid concentrations :

$$-d[MB^+]/dt = \{k'_o + k'_c [C_{16}TAB]\} [MB^+] \quad (9)$$

$$= k''_o [MB^+] \quad (10)$$

where $k'_c = k_c [N\text{-chloro-}p\text{-toluenesulfonamide}]^{3/2}$ and $k''_o = \{k'_o + k'_c [C_{16}TAB]\}$.

If eq. (10) holds, a plot of the observed pseudo-first order rate constant in the presence of catalyst, k''_o vs $[C_{16}TAB]$ should give a straight line with intercept equal to k'_o .

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